

Private Schooling Preference Over Public Schooling (Research Methodology and report writing)

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Abstract

Private schooling is an important feature of the educational landscape in Pakistan and is increasingly a topic of public and government discourse. (Quynh Nguyen, Dhushyanth Raju, 2014) Two types of educational institutions are working in Pakistan to provide education to children's. Government trying to make equal education system across the Pakistan, government announce different educational packages to increase the enrollment rate in public school providing free books, monthly allowances to attract female students and with nominal fee and on the other hand enrolment in private schools has been increasing greatly. (Dawn News, 2014) Private schools have become a necessity for contemporary Pakistani society since the government has failed to provide quality education for its population. A majority of parents, even those from lower income brackets, send their children to private schools so they can receive an education that will enable them to be competitive, (Khan, 2009). Increasingly, parents are responding to perceived inadequate public education by enrolling their children in private schools. There is huge gap between the quality of education and standard being followed in private schools and public school and there are several factors which influence household to get their children's into private schools instead of public school. The question is if both type of schools have flaws and education is free in public sector schools and Government of Pakistan is trying to universalize the school education, then why parents are preferring the private schools (Khan, Noreen & Marriam, 2012). To find out these factors this research has been initiated.

Keywords: private Schooling, Public Schooling

1. Introduction:

The private schools are playing an important role by providing enrollment to 30 percent of the school-going children at national level. (Khan, Noreen & Marriam, 2012). One of the most important ways in which parents are involved in their children's education is through choosing the school they attend. (Ellen Goldring, 2006) Parents choose private schools for their academic and curricula emphases, discipline, and safety (i.e. Bauch, 1988; Erickson, 1986; Greeley, Education in Pakistan is overseen by the Ministry of Education of the Government of Pakistan as well as the provincial, whereas the federal government mostly assists in curriculum development, accreditation and in the financing of research and development. (Wikipedia, 2015) In Pakistan, Punjab has the highest share of private schools with primary grades at 69 percent, followed, in descending order, by Sindh (18 percent), KP (12 percent), and Balochistan (2 percent). (Ministry of Education, 2005).

Private schools are run and own by non-government entities. These schools are providing high quality of education after paying them huge amount of money in form of fees. They hire teachers who can serve their purposes accurately. The private schools may be classified into different categories based on their distinguished characteristics like national chains of private schools and local schools, English medium schools and schools where English is taught from class one but medium of instructions is Urdu, co-educated schools up to 10 years education and segregated schools, the schools offering foreign certificates of schooling like O- level and A-level and schools offering certificates of local educational boards and residential and non-residential private schools. (Ali khan, 2012)

On the other hand public sector schools have specific characteristics like they have purpose built buildings, trained staff and uniform contents of courses, etc. But there is a shocking picture of quality of public schools in Pakistan. Some of the private schools are of good quality but majority of the private schools are not providing good quality education. Similarly public sector schools are producing bulk of the outcome but schools have many flaws. Both public and private schools have flaws and education is free in public sector schools and Government of Punjab is trying to universalize the school education, then why parents are preferring (or not) the private schools. The factors causing their preference will be analyzed in this research and if private schools are preferred then the policy of free education needs some addition to attain universalization of school education. (Ali khan, 2012)

2. Broad Problem Area

Education is the responsibility of Governments. The Government of Pakistan is trying to get the target of universalization of school education for the purpose a number of schemes are going on like the free education, stipends to the students and so on. There is no more success to significantly enhance the enrolment in public sector schools. We see today's everyone in hike to get their children's admission into the private school. The broader problem area is Household preference of private schooling over public schooling.

3. Problem statement

What are the factors contributes towards household preference to private schooling over public schooling?

4. Literature review

A wealth of theoretical and empirical research exists on the effectiveness of private versus public schools. In Pakistan, private schooling is generally considered to be of superior quality as opposed to state-run government schools, (Andrabi, Das & Khawaja, 2006). Private school phenomena involves analyzing the service they provide and comparing it concretely with the alternative(s), especially public schools. Boys are more likely to be enrolled in private schools than girls within the household. She also finds that private schools are of better quality and more effective in imparting quantitative and linguistic skills, (Monazza, 2009).

Joseph L Bast et al. (2004) examined how economic principles predict parents would do a better job choosing schools for their children and concluded that that parents can choose the best schools for their children is collaborated by economic theory and empirical research. Andrabi et al. (2002) investigated that private schools particularly at primary level have an important factor in elementary education of children. Rural urban gap largely exists in private education. He concluded that private schools are not an urban elite phenomenon. They are affordable to middle and even low income groups and (Alderman, 2001) pointed out that poorest parents send their children to private schools in Pakistan rural.

Yasmeen et al. (2011) examine parent's choice of private versus public schooling of their children as an outcome of different family size parent's characteristics, child's characteristics and school characteristics and concluded that there is strong preference for private schools not only in the higher income class but economic class particularly in urban areas in Punjab province of Pakistan.

As family income and parents' levels of education rise, so does the propensity to choose a private school (Buddin, Cordes, & Kirby, 1998). Research suggests parents are concerned with school demographics in their information gathering and choice making (Hamilton & Guin, 2006). Family decision by using choice theoretic framework and concluded that household income, parental education are important factors in shaping household's decision for their children schooling in Pakistan (Nadeem & Arfan, 1999). The household choice of private versus public sector schools as an outcome of child, household and school characteristics by using logit model. The study found that income of the household, education of the parents; English as medium of

instruction in school and distance of public school from the household enhance the preference of private schooling (Ejaz, 2012).

The consensus from studies of the relative effectiveness of public versus private schools in developing countries is that the predicted performance of children in private schools is higher than predicted performance in government schools (Cox and Jimenez (1991), Jimenez, Lockheed and Paqueo (1991), Kingdon (1996b)).

Aram et al. (2008) conducted a study related to the socio – economic factors which affected the parent’s decision towards the school choice for their children in Punjab province. Further the study concluded that parent’s education, and income was positively and strongly influenced the private school enrolment. In urban areas, parents enrolled their children in private school.

Family income is another demographic indicator that has been positively related to choosing private schools. Family income is often thought of as an indicator of resources (Yang & Kayaardi, 2004). Some parents may choose schools in an attempt to increase their satisfaction with their children’s schools. For example, parents might choose a school—public or private—because they are dissatisfied with their child’s previous school. Thus, in a sense, they are choosing away from a certain school or school type in hopes that they might be more satisfied with an alternative to their current situation (Martinez, Thomas, & Kemerer, 1994).

The school quality, school cost and the public/private choice of low-income households in Quetta (Pakistan) have been probed by Alderman, et al. The school attributes, proximity and fees across neighborhood are used to identify the factors which affect poor household’s decision to send their children to government schools, private schools or no-school. The results indicated that even the poorest households use private schools extensively and their utilization increases with income. The study further concluded that lowering private school fees, distance and raising quality may enhance private school enrolment, partly by transfer from government schools and partly by new enrolments (Alderman, 2003). When participating in the school choice marketplace, parents often rely on two types of networks to inform their choices about their children’s education. The first is includes information gathered from people they know from their neighborhood and other social groups. We refer to this type of social networks as “interpersonal networks.” The second type of network addresses the extent to which parents rely on publicly available information such as brochures and pamphlets, public meetings, published results of test scores by school, school and district websites, etc. We call this type of access to important information “formal networks.” The social network literature demonstrates that interpersonal networks are efficient means of gathering information (Schneider, Teske, Rock, & Marschall, 1997).

The rise in private schooling has stirred a debate on the merits and possible demerits of this expansion. On the positive side, the private sector offers a cost-effective means of providing education,1 thereby filling the void created by the inadequate supply (both in terms of quality and quantity) of public education services (Tooley & Dixon, 2006) .

Charter school research suggests that parents choose for the promise of smaller class size, which parents believe will provide better educational quality (Kleitzi, Weiher, Tedin, & Matland, 2000). A survey 56% Pakistanis Prefer Private Schools; However 70% Send Their Children to Government Schools, Gilani Poll/Gallup Pakistan, (2009)

5. Methodology:

To understand the phenomenon of factors contributing towards household preference of private schooling over public schooling a qualitative approach has been used in this research. For identifying the factors the literature was reviewed and interviews were taken. The purpose of study was exploratory because there were many factors which were identified in the literature and to explore more about the existing body of knowledge the research was conducted. According to research design at the first phase broader problem area of research as an interest was identified and then research interview questions were developed. At the second phase, to support the research question grounded theory approach was used. Grounded theory is a set of rigorous research procedures leading to the emergence of conceptual categories (Barney G. Glaser, 2014)

The population was the parents of the private schools of Islamabad and Rawalpindi. Unit of analysis taken as dyads. Interviews taken from the mothers and fathers of children’s because both Mother and Father as parents contributes equally to make choice about their child education. The purposive sampling technique was used because only those parents can be interviewed whose child’s are studying in private school. This is an appropriate method for this type of research in terms of cost and the efficiency of data collection because very limited time was given to accomplish this research. According to Creswell (2007), for purposive sampling techniques under Grounded theory approach the required sample size is 20-30, 12 respondents were selected purposively in convenience sampling as 6 dyads. 6 were mothers of children’s and 6 were father who children’s were studying in the private schools of Rawalpindi and Islamabad for this level of research depends on the cost and time available to the researcher.

The setting for this study was non-contrived as the investigations were carried out in a natural environment. The time horizon was cross sectional because the data is collected in one time within a month due to shortage of time.

Theoretical Framework:

Independent variable:**Moderating Variable****Dependent Variable**

H1: Teacher and student relationship in private school increase the preference

H2: Medium of instruction in private school increase household preference

H3: Security of the children in private school increases the household preference

H4: Strong Assessment System in private schools increase the household preference

6. Results and Conclusion:

This research contributes to the factors regarding parents make school choice of their children's. As a result of conducting unstructured interviews to answer the research question most of the factors were repeated as were reviewed in the literature but few new factors identified. The major new factors identified was the security of the school and the child in the private school. This was described differently by the parents as some respondents said that they feel their children's secure in the private school premises and some said their children's are secure under the private school administration and teachers. Research results show that educated parents prefer private schooling for their children. The distance of the public sector schools tends the parents to send their children to private schools. Another new factor which was indicated by the interview is the social status described as they want their children's to be studied in the private schools to maintain their social status. They said they admit their children's in the private schools and they feel satisfied with their education teaching system compare to public schools. Research have found that children from educated parents are more likely to go to private schools. Few respondents said that assessment system of private schools is much better than public schools and the care of children's is taken much better in private schools.

Moreover school choice question shows that parents prefer the school quality. Parents said that in private schools the child would get more skills, discipline and supervision and which would result in better outcome. Lastly researcher find small but significant household income effects on school choice.

7. Recommendations:

The broader problem area can be resolved with the equilibrium of private and public school policies. Government should also take initiatives to deprived areas where there is no adequate public schools and also private schools charging high with fee for the services.

The public sector policy for universalization of school education is partial failure and need modification by inclusion of more public sector schools with improved quality of education. For the lower per-capita income group, the public sector schools are necessary to attain the target of universalization of school education.

Lastly, this paper has contributed in identifying the factors which make household to prefer private schooling over public schooling of their children's. This research work can be used for further studies to explore more factors or by keeping these factors in mind to find the solution of the problem.

8. Limitations:

The data in our study have some noticeable limitations related to the sampling size that suggests our findings should be interpreted with caution. There were few respondents who were reluctant to record their interviews so researcher took the notes of what they have said. Our sample is drawn from the household of private schools. We do not know about the public school choice in contrast. Time was limited to conduct this research as it has to been done in short period of one month. And also cost had limitation to conduct the interviews from more than possible respondents.

9. List of Random Question asked from respondents:

- Q. what is your name?
- Q. what is your education level?
- Q. How many children's do you have?
- Q. In which school your child is enrolled, weather in public or private school?
- Q. Why you prefer private school instead of public school for your children's?
- Q. what you like most in private school education of your child?

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